

DEVELOPMENT OF THE INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION AMONG STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The aim of the research is to reveal the role of intercultural communicative tolerance in the formation of the individual as well as to present a specially designed technology as part of “Foreign Language” learning. The relevance of this research highlights the necessity to shift the emphasis in the foreign language learning process towards practical-oriented learning targeting the development of personal qualities.*

Keywords: *intercultural communicative tolerance, development technology, communication-oriented learning, multilingual educational environment*

Modern society is characterized by diversity and openness; therefore, the efforts of many organizations, including educational institutions, are aimed at international cooperation and developing partnerships in solving common problems. One way to implement such interactions within higher education institutions is the internationalization of the educational process by attracting foreign students to Russian universities. In this regard, the need for Russian students to speak a foreign language is insufficient. They also need to be eager to have intercultural communications based on respect of human dignity and individuality. In addition, they should be open to other cultures, able to show empathy, possess necessary skills to prevent conflicts, and to resolve them in non-violent ways.

There is a contradiction between the requirements of the Federal State Standard of Higher Education, approved by the Russian Federation Ministry of Education and Science, regarding the need to develop students' general cultural competencies, and the insufficiently developed theoretical and methodological technologies aimed, in particular, at the development of intercultural communicative tolerance within a university. The aim of this research is to reveal the role of intercultural communicative tolerance in the formation of the individual as well as to identify the features of the development of students' intercultural communicative tolerance in the university multilingual educational environment through foreign language learning.

Intercultural communicative tolerance can be considered as a kind of tolerance that is manifested in the process of interpersonal and intercultural communication. In addition, examining it from the point of view of belonging to the intercultural communicative competence, it is defined as “a stable conscious meaningful personal quality, implying a neutral attitude to differences based on the absence of prejudices, expressed in readiness for the implementation of interpersonal and intercultural communication based on respect, understanding, recognition and acceptance of differences, accompanied by the absence of fear to express and defend one's own point of view”. Consequently, the role of intercultural communicative tolerance can not be overemphasized as it represents a significant social and professional quality needed for the formation of a personality having both the needed orientation values and communication skills.

The practice of intercultural interaction shows that people cannot always achieve mutual understanding. This is due to various cultural traditions, norms of behavior, and standards adopted

in their cultures. Therefore, due to the lack of understanding and acceptance of certain norms, there may be disagreements and even hostility towards each other, which indicates a low intercultural communicative competence (ICC). Analysis of I.A. Zimnyaya's, I.L. Pluzhnik's, O.A. Leontovich's works, allows determining the structure of a foreign language ICC that contains the following components:

1. General culture (knowledge and possession of the general cultural system by values characteristic of different countries).
2. Linguistic culture (knowledge and possession of lexical and grammatical units of a foreign language, the ability to extract cultural and historical information).
3. Socio-cultural (knowledge of verbal and non-verbal means, observance of ethical and etiquette speech norms, knowledge of the national character, worldviews, psychology and mentality, tolerance as acceptance of the studied culture and a sense of respect for this culture).
4. Professional (knowledge of skills in the professional sphere, the ability to apply knowledge in a communication with a representative of another culture).

The project work on a foreign language covers the knowledge of different humanitarian subjects, such as music literature, the history of art culture, which allows considering this method and as an effective means of expanding the professional horizon through information obtained from foreign sources. "Project technology is interaction in the course of training and learning in the system of social interaction, in which students take on not only individual, but also collective responsibility for solving collective tasks. It creates conditions that not only increase the volume of knowledge of future specialists, but also their mobility, creativity, and autonomy" [8]. Educational-speech situations "are defined as a set of speech conditions necessary for the student to correctly perform a speech action in accordance with the intended communicative task" [8]. Speech situation is made based on studied foreign texts or in the process of discussing certain topics that provide communicative motivation and relevance of speech activity. Educational and speech situations (the situation of a business meeting with a native speaker, or the situation of staying in a foreign country, etc.) contribute to the modeling of "live speech" and the establishment of contacts with the native speaker. Along with the traditional types of work, the professional skills of the future specialist are formed – analytical reading the texts on the specialty, participation in discussions, writing abstracts, a public presentation with a report. This creates a problematic situation, which activates thinking and serves to generate speech. In addition, extracurricular activities (collection of material for wall newspapers, parties, students scientific-practical conference in a foreign language) give an opportunity to express themselves, help to develop a value attitude to language as parts of culture, increase the interest of students in the study of foreign languages. Formation of intercultural communicative competence among students implies awareness of the native culture and other cultures, their interrelationships; ability and readiness for communication prevent conflicts that inevitably arise from such contacts; the ability to build new patterns of behavior, based on the values and norms of different cultures. It assumes the development of such personal qualities as patience, the ability to empathy, and tolerance.

As part of the research, the levels of intercultural communicative tolerance formation (high, middle and low) with their distinguishing features were developed. The high level of students' intercultural communicative tolerance has the following characteristics: students' knowledge of their own rights; a high degree of students' awareness of the essential and meaningful characteristics of tolerance (having in-depth knowledge); knowledge of the specifics of conducting

equal dialogue at the interpersonal and intercultural levels; awareness of the right of any person to be different and to have one's own opinion; the formation of one's own attitude towards the concept of 'tolerance'; neutral or positive attitude to the personality differences; a positive attitude towards the development of tolerance as a valuable characteristic of the individual; accepting oneself as a tolerant person; a marked desire for equal dialogue; active use of methods of tolerant interpersonal and intercultural interaction; showing positive reaction to the personality differences and expressing benevolence towards others. The middle level of students' intercultural communicative tolerance has the following characteristics: partial students' knowledge of their own rights; lack of students' awareness of the essential and meaningful characteristics of tolerance (having perfunctory knowledge); insufficient knowledge of the specifics of conducting an equal dialogue; ambiguous attitude to the rights of other people; ambiguous attitude to the concept of 'tolerance'; negative attitude to the personality differences; ambiguous attitude towards the development of tolerance as a valuable characteristic of the individual; uncertainty in accepting oneself a tolerant personal; implicitly expressed desire for equal dialogue; inactive use of methods of tolerant interpersonal and intercultural interaction; showing negative reactions to the personality differences and expressing malevolence towards others. The low level of students' intercultural communicative tolerance has the following characteristics: lack of students' knowledge of their own rights; a low degree of students' awareness of the essential and meaningful characteristics of tolerance (lack of in-depth knowledge); lack of students' knowledge of the specifics of conducting an equal dialogue; unwillingness to accept the human right to be different and to have one's own opinion; the lack of one's own attitude towards the concept of 'tolerance'; extremely negative attitude to the personality differences; a negative attitude towards the development of tolerance as a valuable characteristic of the individual; unwillingness to accept oneself as a tolerant person; lack of desire for equal dialogue; failure to use the methods of tolerant interpersonal and intercultural interaction; showing negative reactions to the personality differences and expressing aggression towards others. In order to elaborate tolerance, the intercultural communicative tolerance development technology was specially designed and applied in the foreign language classes at the university.

The orientation of the educational process on the competent content of education assumes the formation not only of communicative competence, but also of competences related to life in a multipolar world, designed to prevent the emergence of misunderstanding, alienation and spread of xenophobia. 235 Formation of the students' ability of foreign ICC is carried out in the process of teaching all types of speech activity (reading, speaking, writing, and listening) both in the course of classroom activities and in the course of out-of-class work. The main goal is to prepare students for the use of a foreign language in professional and scientific activities, which involves equipping students with the necessary minimum professional vocabulary, knowledge of the basics of professional activities related to the use of a foreign language, and the basis of ICC.

REFERENCES

1. Akhmadullina, R. M., Abdrafikova, A. R., & Vanyukhina, N. V. (2016). The use of music as a way of formation of communicative skills of students in teaching English language. *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, 11(6), 1295-1302.

2. Mukhametzyanova, L., & Svirina, L. (2016). Intercultural Citizenship and English Classroom Language. *Journal of Organizational Culture, Communications and Conflict*, 20, Special Issue, 256-262.
3. Fahrutdinova, R. A., Yarmakeev, I. E., & Fakhruddinov, R. R. (2014). The Formation of Students' Foreign Language Communicative Competence during the Learning Process of the English Language through Interactive Learning Technologies (The Study on the Basis of Kazan Federal University). *English Language Teaching*, 7(12), 36-46.
4. Petrikova A., Kuprina T., Beketova A., Mishenkova M. Intercultural aspects of concept "TOLERANCE" and facilities of creating tolerant academic environment. *XLinguae. European Scientific Language Journal* [Internet]. 2017 [cited 2018 Jan 15]; 10 (4): 287–303. Available from: http://www.xlinguae.eu/2017_10_04_24.html
5. Mamatkadirovna K. N. JARAYONIDA TALABALARNING KOMMUNIKATIV FAOLIYATINI SHAKILLANTIRISHDA TA'LIM INFORMASION TEXNOLOGIYADAN FOYDALANISH //Ta'lim fidoyilari. – 2022. – T. 18. – №. 5. – С. 338-341.
6. Mamatkadirovna N. K. Pedagogical system of development of culture of international communication in students //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 11. – №. 11. – С. 245-247.
7. Reid E. Defining terms and interconnections between culture, communication and language teaching. *A Trimestrial European Scientific Language Review*. 2011; 1: 43–54.
8. Mamatkadirovna A. K. et al. Translation as a Special Type of Language and Intercultural Communication //JournalNX. – С. 176-180.
9. Meng X. Teaching Russian language in PRC as socio-cultural problem. In: Proceedings of the XII Congress of the International Association of Teachers of the Russian Language and Literature, MAPRYAL 2011; 2011 May 8–11; Shanghai, China. p. 111–114.
10. Karimova N. Professional and moral competence of primary school teachers: essence, structure, content //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – T. 7. – №. 11.
11. Kuprina T., Minasyan S. Geouristics as new branch of geocultural space. *XLinguae. European Scientific Language Journal* [Internet]. 2014 [cited 2018 Feb 02]; 7 (4): 2–20.
12. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal. - 2021. - P. 209-214.
13. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." *International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education* 1 (2020): 6-15.
14. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).
15. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –T., "Shaffof", 2023, 416-bet.
16. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – T. 48. – №. 12.
17. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
18. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at

- university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
19. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
 20. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.